

The Impact of Museum Architecture on Urban Development through Social Interaction: The Case of the Museum of Ethnography

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Abstract

Cities unite diverse communities, cultures, and activities, fostering socio-cultural life and evolving through social processes. A city's physical structure and its social dynamics exist in a symbiotic relationship, necessitating analyses that extend beyond economic and technical activities to include physical, cultural, and social formations supported by architectural space and the communicative qualities of these relationships. This article foregrounds an interdisciplinary perspective, focusing on the potential of museum architecture to contribute to urban development by structuring social interaction through its physical and spatial configurations. To explore this potential, the Budapest: Museum of Ethnography Museum was selected as a case study and analysed through architectural description. As part of Europe's largest cultural urban development initiative, the museum exemplifies a design that produces urban commons and enhances urban quality of life through its interior-exterior integration. This serves as a significant example of how an architectural object, rather than being solely a symbolic entity, an attraction or a prestige element, can function as an open social interaction space accessible to all, thereby ensuring the continuity of public spaces and supporting urban development. The study contributes a holistic perspective on the relationship between societal processes and spatial configurations, extending from interior spaces to the urban scale.

Keywords

Museum architecture, urban development, social interaction, urban regeneration, Budapest Museum of Ethnography

Introduction

The wave of globalisation that emerged after the Second World War, coupled with the increased frequency of economic crises, prompted nations to implement stability policies aimed at macroeconomic variables such as employment and production. From the 1980s onwards, economic crises in Europe have increasingly incorporated cultural dimensions, recognising the role of intangible social capital in fostering stability. Cultural activities were prioritised for their

potential to enhance economic growth and performance, alongside efforts to encourage investment in human capital and innovation. In 1993, the European Union's white paper *Growth, Competitiveness and Employment: The Challenges and Ways Forward into the 21st Century* identified cultural activities as central to six of the sectors with the most promising employment prospects. Subsequently, the 2005 OECD report *Culture and Local Development* highlighted the contribution of cultural activities to the economic development of countries, regions and communities. This was followed in 2007 by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) publication *Managing Creative Industries*, which emphasised the significance of cultural activities for economic growth and the protection of intellectual property. Similarly, the 2008 United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) report *Creative Activities* underscored cultural activities as one of the primary drivers of growth. Together, these reports underscore the critical importance of cultural activities for economic development (Grefe, 2011: 121).

Support for local development in regions that have lost their core cultural activities has extended beyond the national scale, enhancing their appeal, strengthening their image, fostering new initiatives, and generating employment and income. In European cities, efforts to achieve regional cohesion by leveraging local identity and enhancing competitiveness through culture, arts and natural environment initiatives have necessitated the evolution of these organisational structures, including cultural tourism. Consequently, museums, once considered declining institutions in the 1960s but revived from the 1980s onwards as influential platforms for cultural presentation (Huysen, 1995/1999: 30), have become central to such activities. However, artistic and architectural transformations during this period accelerated the commodification of urban spaces, the creation of urban icons, and the establishment of focal points in public spaces catering to specific social groups (Güneş, 2024: 88). Museums were no longer expected to function solely as spaces for memory, culture and art but also as education centres, shopping venues, urban flagships, fundraising mechanisms, tools for urban planning and local development, engines of mass entertainment, and even instruments of diplomacy. To achieve their fundamental cultural objectives, education, exhibition, preservation and conservation, museums had to address issues such as competitiveness, visitor management, and resource generation (Vivant, 2011: 99, 102). The symbolic value of museums has therefore been reinforced through iconic architecture. Their appeal as sectors within the "creative industries" of mass tourism and neoliberal markets has often overshadowed their societal role. Major cities have engaged in a "museum race," showcasing spectacular architecture by "starchitects" in the form of "superstar" museums (Grefe and Pflieger, 2005: 67; Vivant, 2011: 102; Brown and Mairesse, 2018: 531; Nieroba, 2017: 95). Notable examples include Herzog & de Meuron's Tate Modern, transformed from a former power station into a global cultural landmark in London; Zaha Hadid's

MAXXI Museum in Rome, which revitalised a former military zone as a hub for artistic activities, exhibitions, workshops, and social interactions; and Coop Himmelblau's Musée des Confluences, the centrepiece of Lyon's industrial and port area regeneration. While such projects in Western and Southern Europe are often funded through public-private partnerships, Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries typically rely on EU grants, international collaborations, or government subsidies due to limited funding. Although this funding disparity has reduced the number of iconic museum projects in CEE countries, it has not hindered their role in fostering regional tourism and enhancing international visibility. In recent years, however, global policies have faced growing scrutiny, driven by concerns over the weakening and homogenisation of local cultures and identities, diminishing accessibility to visible commodities, and renewed attention to spatial equity and inclusivity (Güneş, 2024: 68, 88). Critiques of the local adaptability of global products and policies, and the incorporation of local culture into sustainable strategies, have encouraged the preservation of cultural diversity. In this context, one of the most significant debates in the built environment concerns the inclusivity of local identity in museum architecture and spatial design.

Therefore, interventions and productions that diverge from conventional design methods and practices, those that position urban dwellers as active agents within the urban environment, engage in participatory actions connected to everyday life, and stretch the social boundaries of urban space, have the potential to foster continuous encounters and interactions. Such approaches can enable new forms of urban consciousness and citizenship (Sözgen, 2021: 103). Consequently, the complex structure of cities should be analysed not only through economic and technical activities but also through the physical, cultural and social formations supported by architectural space, as well as the communicative nature of these relationships. Within this framework, the relationship between the city, museums and society can be re-evaluated. The processes of commodification and societal detachment that museums have undergone can be transformed by restructuring social interaction through the physical and spatial configurations of museum architecture. According to Tzortzi, this transformation, which involves interpreting the museum phenomenon through the concept of urban sociality, introduces a new understanding of the "urbanised museum." This concept envisions museums as spaces that are open to the city, connected to people and focused on creating perspectives and experiences rather than transmitting specific messages (Tzortzi, 2018: 1; Tzortzi, 2024).

Building on this foundation, the study examines how the permeable relationship between museum architecture and the city can be established through physical and spatial arrangements. It explores how spatial behaviour and everyday social life can be directed in either conditional or unrestricted ways, thereby achieving public sustainability. This analysis is centred on the Budapest: Museum of Ethnography, which, while designed with national and local codes,

has gained international recognition as a representation of a new model of museum architecture. The museum's role as part of a government-supported urban transformation project adds further significance. Historically, in Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries, economic rationalism was widely accepted and implemented, particularly under the influence of international organisations. However, following the 1989 transition from centrally planned economies, EU accession processes and pressures from international bodies have shifted governmental priorities towards increasing accessibility and equality, fostering greater social cohesion, and improving societal welfare (Scott, 2006: 69; Bohle and Greskovits, 2007). The study has two main objectives: To theoretically elucidate the role of museums in urban transformation and to present museum architecture as an example of the "urbanised museum" concept. This concept reflects contemporary global trends in social interaction and the continuity of public space, making the findings relevant to an international audience. In this sense, the study questions are formulated as follows:

- Can urban transformation projects enhance urban quality of life while increasing social interaction and civic participation?
- How do museums function as spaces of interaction that facilitate greater public engagement in the urban realm?
- How does the architectural design of museums support the social and cultural participation of urban communities?

Museum (Architecture) as an Asset for Urban Development and Social Interaction

Urban renewal projects, often regarded as key strategies for addressing the effects of urban decline and economic restructuring, carry high expectations. Their success is frequently measured by the capacity of the museums involved to build strong brands and attract investments in an increasingly competitive global arena (Plaza and Haarich, 2009: 3). Entering the 21st century, major cities have promoted high-profile cultural events and initiatives through the construction of "cultural venues," "cultural quarters" (Grefe and Pflieger, 2005: 11), or "museum quarters," which have become tangible symbols of urban transformation (Lazzeroni et al., 2013: 454). Cultural quarters are designed to achieve several objectives: strengthening the identity, appeal, and competitiveness of cities; fostering an entrepreneurial approach to the arts and culture by positioning culture as a strategic lever for creativity; repurposing dilapidated or decaying sites; and promoting cultural democracy and diversity (Grefe and Pflieger, 2005: 9). Industrial areas, particularly those with a high number of buildings in need of rehabilitation, have undergone transformation into cultural cities, becoming attractive destinations for external visitors while also appealing to the local population and skilled workers through the establishment of prestigious museums and exhibitions (Heidenreich and Plaza, 2015: 1448–

1449). In a consumer society, the musealisation of culture, the transformation of the museum itself into a discursive practice, and its globalisation facilitate the generation of direct and indirect economic impacts. While these impacts can be positive, supporting cultural industries and the sustainability of cultural heritage, they may also result in negative outcomes, including commercialisation, the loss of artistic value, and increased inequality. As a result, balanced approaches prioritising the preservation of cultural identity, the sustainability of local values, and social participation are increasingly necessary.

One of the most notable examples of urban renewal projects, which introduced the concept of the "Bilbao Effect" into the literature, is the Guggenheim Museum Bilbao. Designed by Frank Gehry, the museum's iconic architecture is perceived as a successful symbol of urban and economic revitalisation, structural transformation, a renewed image and city branding. However, according to Foster, the prominence of the Guggenheim Museum as the first visible sign upon entering the city demonstrates the museum's circulation as a logo. Foster argues that this should not be interpreted as a success story but rather as a reflection of the inflation of design and display and a component of today's culture of spectacle. Furthermore, the architectural and spatial configuration described on Bilbao's official website as a "large sculpture made of titanium, limestone and glass" (Guggenheim Museum Bilbao, n.d.) has transformed the museum into an extravagant, oversized venue capable of overwhelming both art and audiences (Foster, 2002/2017: 45, 56). The inability of local residents to see themselves reflected in the museum and their disbelief that it represents Basque culture (Vivant, 2011: 110) highlights the negative interaction between the museum and the local community. Certain urban renewal projects, which can also be viewed as manifestations of global capital competition within urban spaces, often bring gentrification, as seen in the Bilbao example. The OECD's 2024 project *Space for Culture: Guidance for Cities, Developers and Creative Sectors* and its collaboration with the International Council of Museums (ICOM) in the 2019 guide *Culture and Local Development: Maximising the Impact—A Guide for Local Governments, Communities and Museums* address this phenomenon. They outline the risks associated with urban renewal projects, including the development of cultural districts: The necessity of affordable housing due to population and economic growth, subsidising rents for workshop spaces, tailoring innovation, start-up, and business development services to the needs of creative professionals, and improving connectivity through investments in transport infrastructure. According to Vivant (2011: 100), while prestigious museums can be used as tools for urban planning and development, the belief that museums can "save" a city is a myth. The growing trend of indiscriminately using the Bilbao example as a benchmark for public policy has led to the proliferation of diverse models, some of which are not universally applicable. Cities such as Sheffield (United Kingdom), Newcastle upon Tyne (United Kingdom), Milwaukee (United States), León (Spain), and Herford (Germany) are

examples of urban renewal projects with inefficient operations that have resulted in failure or crisis. Plaza and Haarich (2009: 4) identify three categories of conditions that must be met for a museum to have a successful impact on the local or regional economy and become an economic activator: a) Basic locational and economic conditions. b) Conditions related to the public policy framework of action. c) Conditions related to the museum project and its management. These conditions are interconnected and equally significant. Considering that effective urban culture is shaped by the processes of communication and interaction, which cannot exist independently of space (Demir Kahraman, 2019: 195), the entire iconography of public space—from the quality of spatial design and architectural expression to patterns of use and public gathering routines—(Amin, 2008: 13) becomes essential. Therefore, museums should not be viewed solely as standalone icons, symbols or works of art but rather as sites for all sorts of sense-making social actions (Jones and MacLeod, 2016: 212). Today, museums are increasingly expected to address social exclusion, build social capital and engage with social issues to promote community development (Nieroba, 2017: 90). They are also seen as meeting points for people from different social and cultural classes and ethnic groups within urban spaces, providing inclusive environments for all. These growing societal responsibilities underscore the need for a sociological and descriptive analysis of museum architecture.

The current professional definition of a museum is provided by the International Council of Museums (ICOM). In 2022, during the Extraordinary General Assembly of ICOM held in Prague, the definition was updated to reflect global developments, the evolving role of museums and institutional governance models. The new definition states: "A museum is a not-for-profit, permanent institution in the service of society that researches, collects, conserves, interprets, and exhibits tangible and intangible heritage. Open to the public, accessible and inclusive, museums foster diversity and sustainability. They operate and communicate ethically, professionally and with the participation of communities, offering varied experiences for education, enjoyment, reflection and knowledge sharing." (ICOM, n.d.) This multifaceted definition highlights a museum model that is positively oriented towards society, prioritising social interaction. Citizens are now considered the primary focus and central participants in the museum's objectives and activities.

Architecture is inherently social, occupied by different groups in varying ways. Museum architecture, in particular, is a social process, existing in a constant state of production through the actions of an interconnected network of actors who are the authors of its meanings (Jones and MacLeod, 2016: 208). The holistic approach observed in contemporary architecture, where public and private uses intersect, spatial boundaries blur, and a broader urban surface is designed and programmed, supports this production, moving from the internal to the external (or vice versa) (Gönül, 2022: 801). In this context, the narrative unfolds not through the physical

arrangement of spaces or the placement of exhibits, but in response to the movement of visitors. This inward-to-outward experience allows for a holistic perception of the museum. Conversely, a formal existence that distances the museum from its urban context, hindering visual and physical connections and positioning it as a detached element, renders the museum experience exclusionary and divisive for visitors. The scale of the museum can further complicate this exclusionary role through its rigid structural boundaries, sheer size and lack of public spaces and accessibility. Such characteristics diminish its capacity to foster inclusivity and connection within the urban environment.

All this information underscores the necessity of supporting culture-centred holistic approaches to urban development goals with architecture that fosters community participation, social interaction, and cultural vibrancy. The national and regional architectural policies¹ developed within the European Union member states in the context of design quality are a result of these requirements. According to a research report supported by the Architects' Council of Europe (ACE) and funded by the European Union (Bento, 2023), the primary benefit of these policies lies in the development of "a new range of informal tools of urban design governance that did not exist beforehand in some countries, such as new awareness-raising and educational initiatives, as well as the greater use of awards schemes, design review panels, architecture competitions, etc." Hungary is among the European countries that, in 2015, formulated a comprehensive and strategic policy formalising architecture as an object of public policy in the form of a strategy or program. This policy summarised the government's ambitions regarding architecture and the design of the built environment. Budapest, the capital of Hungary, stands out in its long-term urban development plans (targeted for 2030) with a vision of becoming "the leading economic power, an innovation and cultural centre of Central and Eastern Europe, the leader in knowledge and creative economic development." The city also aims to be "a versatile capital city, offering a high quality of life and equal opportunities to its residents" (Budapest Municipality, n.d.). In line with this vision, the renewal of existing green spaces and urban areas has been addressed through the Liget Budapest project, Hungary's largest cultural development initiative in the last century. The project includes the creation of a new museum district and recreational activity areas. This study focuses on the Budapest: Museum of Ethnography, one of the project's flagship buildings, analysing its architecture from a social perspective.

¹ "An architectural policy can be defined as a public policy promoting the quality of architecture and the built environment, which includes the design of buildings, public spaces, infrastructure and all the elements that constitute the living environment. Considering its broad scope, it cuts across the different policy areas that affect the design quality of the built environment, such as building, urban planning, environment, cultural heritage, public works, among others. This means it comprises the different levels and sectors of the state as well as other stakeholders that intervene in the processes of designing and managing the built environment (Bento, 2023: 19)."

Methodology

The prioritisation of culture in the development policies and strategies of local governments reveals a tendency to shape social interactions between the city, museums and society through architectural design. To explore this tendency, the study focuses on Budapest. Since the 1990s, Budapest has been associated with culture and the arts, while branding campaigns in the 2000s predominantly promoted its thermal baths and Hungarian gastronomy. However, following Hungary's accession to the European Union in 2004 and the introduction of low-cost airline routes, the city saw an increased focus on non-cultural activities -such as low-cost alcohol and parties- alongside its cultural, architectural, museum, heritage, and health-related offerings. From 2013 onwards, Budapest became a weekend party destination, with tourists as the primary consumers. The bureaucratic barriers to developing tourism in other areas negatively impacted urban planning (Smith et al., 2022: 6-7). Urban policies that led to widespread deprivation and exclusion among social groups brought renewed attention to inclusive approaches prioritising culture and the design of public spaces. Within this context, the Budapest: Museum of Ethnography, previously discussed, was selected as the study's focal area.

According to Zevi, every building contributes to the creation of two spaces: the interior, defined entirely by the building itself, and the exterior (or urban space), formed between the building and its neighbouring structures. Architecture, or interior space, constitutes the fundamental element of the architectural event, which cannot be learned, experienced, displayed, or represented without direct engagement (Zevi, 1948/2015: 24). In light of this, the study adopts a qualitative approach that emphasises the importance of directly experiencing an architectural product and the personal process of interpretation. This approach highlights the interaction, communication and experience between the researcher and the subject under investigation.

The study is centred on the author's visit to the museum and its surroundings in May 2023, conducted in the capacities of tourist, interior architect, and academic researcher. The research draws on the author's personal experiences, which are interpreted and contextualised within a qualitative case study framework to provide insight into both architectural and urban aspects of the site. Additionally, the study employs traditional data collection methods such as literature review, on-site observation, and photography. Case studies highlight the significance of context, which in this research is examined on two levels: theoretical and spatial. The theoretical context is explained in alignment with global trends, while the spatial context is defined by the socially oriented museum building conceptualised as part of Budapest's urban regeneration, including the repurposing of the city park. The architectural description and analysis are informed by the author's observations as a visitor and user, integrating subjective impressions with analytical interpretation. The analysis emphasises the relationship established between the architectural

interior and the city through physical and visual connections, as well as the meanings created by this interaction. It also evaluates the success of a new architectural design approach that blurs the boundaries between the building and the city/urban space.

Case Study: Museum of Ethnography, Budapest

Capital cities are often regarded as symbolic representations of their nations, reflecting national identity. They hold a distinct advantage in offering diverse products and experiences, frequently serving as the first, and often the only, point of contact for most tourists (Puczkó et al., 2007: 22, 26). Similarly, Budapest functions as Hungary's cultural gateway, a primary destination, and a city integral to the country's international image, particularly for foreign visitors (Smith and Puczkó, 2012: 109). Developments such as the unification of the former cities of Pest, Buda, and Óbuda in 1872–1873 and the completion of the Millennium Underground Railway, the first of its kind in Continental Europe, aligned Budapest with metropolitan roles. The quantity and quality of heritage built during the late 19th and early 20th centuries further solidified its position as a significant cultural hub. These roles have been re-evaluated since the late 1990s, coinciding with Hungary's anticipated accession to the European Union. Budapest's geographical position as a Central European city has established it as a financial, conference and intellectual centre, as well as a gateway city and a bridge connecting Northeast Europe and the Balkans to Western countries (Polyák, 2006: 197).

Figure 1 – Budapest downtown districts and UNESCO World heritage area with buffer zone (created by the author based on UNESCO-Budapest, including the Banks of the Danube, the Buda Castle Quarter and Andrassy Avenue Maps at <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/400/maps/>)

As a clear representation of Hungarian history and culture, part of Budapest—along with its buffer zone—has been designated as a historic monuments area on the UNESCO World Heritage

List since 1987, following Hungary's accession to the World Heritage Convention in 1985, and remains under legal protection. This protected area was further enlarged in 2005, following the extension of the property in 2002, under the Act on the Protection of Cultural Heritage (UNESCO, n.d.; OWHC, n.d.). The boundaries of this area predominantly fall within Districts I, V, VI and VII of Budapest (Figure 1), a city divided into 23 districts. District I in Buda is home to the Castle District, while Districts V, VI and VII in Pest serve as the city's creative industry hub, featuring restaurants, bars, cafes, museums, design shops, arts and crafts markets, and art galleries. Andrassy Avenue, which is included on the World Heritage List for its original 19th-century urban architecture, is located in District VI. Known for its high-end fashion brand retail stores, the avenue connects Pest's historic centre to Heroes' Square (Hősök Tere) and City Park (Városliget), situated near the boundaries of District XIV. During the 2000s, EU subsidies and additional revenues from an improving economy were supported by political will (Rajcsányi, 2023). After 2010, the Hungarian government initiated renewal projects along this axis, encompassing Budapest's most tourist-heavy historic areas. Among the largest government-backed projects are the National Hauszmann Program, which focuses on the reconstruction and restoration of the Buda Castle District, and Liget Budapest, aimed at the development and revitalisation of City Park (Végh, 2017; MacManus, 2015; MacManus, 2013).

Figure 2 – Liget Budapest Project Park map (created by the author based on Liget Budapest official map at <https://ligetbudapest.hu/en/map>)

Museum districts have become an effective tool for urban development and transformation in European cities. By integrating cultural components, these spatial developments facilitate the fusion of buildings and open public spaces within a broader urban environment, a concept that

emerged in the latter half of the 20th century. Renowned and successful examples of museum districts include Museuminsel and Kulturforum in Berlin, MuseumQuartier in Vienna, Kunstareal in Munich, Parkmuseerne in Copenhagen, and Museumplein in Amsterdam. According to Kochergina's typological study (2017: 6), museum districts can be categorised into four types: independent core, neighbourhood, city network and urbanised nature. Independent core describes a model where cultural activities are concentrated in one territorially isolated site; neighbourhood refers to an undefined boundary model where large museums create a magnetic field that gradually attracts new small galleries, cultural centres, and SMEs; city network combines elements of the first two models, focusing on institutional collaboration without creating a distinct interior space. The Liget Budapest project aligns most closely with the urbanised nature model, which involves situating museums within a park of considerable size (Figure 2). While this model offers numerous benefits, it also presents challenges, including preserving green spaces (which are notably scarce in modern urban centres), reconciling the differing atmospheres of museums and parks, and addressing technological, infrastructural, and accessibility requirements. Objections and protests related to preserving the existing green spaces for local residents further emphasise these challenges, as highlighted following the Hungarian government's approval of the Liget Budapest master plan (Végh, 2017). According to a Liget usage survey conducted by Szilágyi (2014), park visitors appreciated the park in its original form and expressed a preference for minor, non-structural changes such as additional park furniture, improved landscape features, increased green areas, and better infrastructure (cited in Szaszak and Kecskes, 2018: 396). This feedback was interpreted² by decision-makers, designers, and implementers not as a call to abandon the project but to prioritise the park as a public space serving local residents, families, people with disabilities, children, and pet owners before functioning as a regional or international tourist attraction. In response to this feedback, some proposed buildings were removed from the programme, while others were selected through an open, transparent, anonymous, two-stage international architectural design competition (McManus, 2014). The process involved extensive civic dialogues (McManus, 2015) and social consultations (Szaszak and Kecskes, 2018: 394). The influence of this socially

² For statements made by László Baán, Ministerial Commissioner for the Liget Budapest Project, and Benedek Gyorgyevics, CEO of Városliget Zrt., regarding the project's implementation, see:

McManus, D. (2015, January 26). Liget Budapest Competition Winners: Liget Budapest Project Design Contest. e-Architect. Retrieved October 18, 2024, from <https://www.e-architect.com/budapest/liget-budapest-project-competition>

Liget Budapest Official Website. (2018, December 05). World's best architecture: Museum of Ethnography. Retrieved October 18, 2024, from https://ligetbudapest.hu/en/archive/worlds-best-architecture-museum-of-ethnography?_gl=1%2a1pwy50k%2a_up%2aMQ..%2a_ga%2aMTYxMTY3OTg4LjE3MjkyNjU5NjM.%2a_ga_QRPJ5Q1DM5%2aMTcyOTI3MzA2OC4yLjAuMTcyOTI3MzA2OC4wLjAuMA

About Hungary Official Website. (2024, September 30). Liget Budapest Acknowledged as 'Best Tourism Development Project'. Retrieved November 13, 2024, from <https://abouthungary.hu/news-in-brief/liget-budapest-acknowledged-as-best-tourism-development-project>

inclusive approach is evident in the features of the winning design for the Budapest: Museum of Ethnography, part of the Liget Budapest project. Designed by Napur Architect Kft.³, the building reflects local desires and the global functions of a 21st-century museum. It embodies accessibility, transparency, dynamism, inclusivity, harmony with nature, and, most importantly, a design philosophy rooted in dialogue and cultural sensitivity.

Figure 3 – Information overview of the Museum of Ethnography (created by the author using a photograph from <https://www.archdaily.com/983318/museum-of-ethnography-budapest-napur-architect>)

The Budapest: Museum of Ethnography (Figure 3) was established in 1872 as the ethnography department of the Hungarian National Museum (Vargyas, 1992: 24) and became an independent institution in 1947 (Apor, 2011: 413). Sponsored by the Hungarian state, the museum remained without a permanent building until its inclusion in the Liget Budapest Project (Fejős, 2001: 24). The museum's location within the park is particularly significant (Figure 4). It lies at the intersection of Király Utca (extending into Városligeti Fásor), which marks the boundary between Districts VI and VII and partially includes the city's tourist party zone and the City Park. This site, directly connected to the historic city, traditionally served as the gateway to the park before the construction of Andrassy Avenue. The area is also home to Ötvenhatosok Square (Ötvenhatosok Tere), which houses the Monument of the 1956 Hungarian Revolution and War of Independence. In 1986, the National Millennium Exhibition commemorating Hungary's thousand-year anniversary was held in this space, marking the first public display of the ethnographic collection in the City Park. This historical and urban significance has profoundly influenced the museum's architectural design. The monument remains preserved at its original location, with the museum building designed around it. The building is divided into two parts

³For further details, see: Napur Architect Official Website; <https://napur.hu/en/munkak/neprajzi-muzeum-atadas/>

above ground, with the monument forming the street-level focal point. This approach demonstrates the museum's alignment with the city's historical memory and its intent to bridge the old and the new, creating a harmonious integration rather than disregarding the past. The building's design also avoids interrupting the flow of the street, instead allowing for a seamless transition into the park. While the museum is situated at a central intersection, its design draws downward, enhancing its role as a gateway and threshold rather than a terminus. This ensures continuity as part of the city's urban network. Unlike exclusionary architectural designs that enclose the park with barriers, the museum's physical-spatial codes render its boundaries legible while simultaneously blurring them. The museum's two sections are connected by a landscaped roof garden, addressing concerns about reduced green space due to new museum constructions within the Liget Budapest project. This roof garden adds 7,300 m² of park-like area, transforming the museum's footprint into a qualitative extension of the park. Rather than losing green space, the museum has become a special and integrated part of the park itself.

Figure 4 – The Museum's location and its direct connection to the historic city (created by the author; dots indicate historic areas, with dot size roughly representing the relative density of historic buildings.)

Hal Foster emphasises that architecture in a global style, which transcends national boundaries, should incorporate traces of local characteristics to convey a sense of belonging to its place (Foster, 2011/2015: 109). In this context, the Budapest: Museum of Ethnography derives much of its sense of place from its frequently praised glass façade. This façade features contemporary reinterpretations of 40 ethnographic motifs selected from the museum's Hungarian and international collections. These motifs are embedded within a raster-patterned metal grid composed of half a million pixels (Liget Budapest, 2021). The museum's official introduction on the Liget Budapest Project's website highlights this feature, inviting visitors to "find a Hungarian folk motif among the pixels, take a photo of it, and post it on Facebook or Instagram with the hashtag #Néprajzmuzeum" (Liget Budapest, n.d.). Such calls encourage engagement with potential visitors through social media platforms, serving as a way to emphasise the museum's references to tangible and intangible heritage and its connection to national values.

Figure 5 – Representation of museum form as a skateboard park and social space (created by the author using photographs from the author's archive)

The recessed central design of the building can be interpreted as conveying metonymic⁴ messages to the city's residents. Skateboarding, often perceived as a form of pure joy, excitement, and self-expression, finds a symbolic counterpart in the museum's architecture. According to Lombard (2016), skateboarding entered mainstream popular media⁵ after the 2000s, becoming an integral part of urban life and culture in contemporary global society. It has also been recognised as a tool for building social capital and addressing societal issues, leading

⁴ Metonymy is defined as the process of mentally accessing one conceptual entity via another entity and involves the cognitive relationship between the reference point and the target (Radden and Kövecses, 1999: 19; Kövecses, 2013: 78).

⁵ For further details, see:

Borden, I. (2015, April 20). The new skate city: How Skateboarders are joining the urban mainstream. The Guardian. Retrieved January 01, 2025, from <https://www.theguardian.com/cities/2015/apr/20/skate-city-skateboarders-developers-bans-defensive-architecture>

Borden, I. (2019). *Skateboarding and the City: A Complete History*. Bloomsbury Publishing.

to the frequent incorporation of skate-friendly designs⁶ in the rehabilitation of urban public spaces and parks. The museum's design reflects this cultural shift by visually expressing its intent to engage with the city's residents and visitors, establishing its public character and sending clear messages about its desire to connect (Figure 5). This approach transforms the urban streets into centres of socialisation and social cohesion, promoting a sense of public benefit through design. The program embedded in the building's design fosters urban commons, dismantling the preconception that museums cater exclusively to the upper class. Instead, it asserts that the museum is open to all, accessible to anyone who seeks engagement. By addressing inclusivity through practice, the museum transcends its conventional institutional boundaries, integrating into the city as a space for everyday life. This redefines the museum's role and highlights its contribution to urban development, positioning it as a shared cultural and social asset.

The building's ascent from its central point to its final height reflects a careful alignment with environmental factors. It remains within the height limits of surrounding structures, avoiding the obstruction of public views of the park and maintaining a connection with its surroundings, rather than severing it through excessive elevation. This design decision is crucial for preserving the city's historical panoramic views. The building's rooftop garden further enhances this experience by offering multiple vantage points for viewing the panoramic scenery. While visitors cannot access these views from street level, the green roof provides an opportunity for exploration, delivering a surprising and immersive experience. By enabling users to perceive the space from different perspectives, the rooftop transforms the visitor's position within and around the building into a state of unity with its architecture, fostering a sense of cohesion and integration.

⁶ For further projects, see "The European Prize for Urban Public Space" competition results at <https://www.publicspace.org/en/the-prize>, especially the project of Westblaak Skate Park (Rotterdam), Micropolis Skate Park (Helsinki), Sk8+U Collaborative Skate Park (Arbúcies).

Figure 6 – Ground and basement floor plans of the Museum of Ethnography with photographs of interior spaces (created by the author using photographs from the author's archive and the plan from <https://www.archdaily.com/983318/museum-of-ethnography-budapest-napur-architect>)

The entrance to the building is located within the boundaries of the park, allowing for various everyday activities to take place at this threshold. This design choice transforms the connection between the interior and the urban space from a purely visual link into an interactive public realm. This interactivity extends into the building through a defined yet symbolic entrance, creating a seamless transition between exterior and interior spaces. The spatial organisation of the museum facilitates the distribution of social life across the ground floor while allocating more specialised functions—such as education, permanent and temporary exhibitions, and seminars—to the basement and upper levels. The museum shop and restaurant exemplify this stratified integration of sociability, drawing visitors into the interior while maintaining a connection with the public realm. This design approach positions the museum not solely as a space dedicated to its primary functions but as an extension of the urban street and park. Supported by its interaction with the surrounding environment, the building operates as a transitional space that bridges the boundaries between the interior and the exterior, blending public and private domains (Figure 6).

The cloakrooms, traditionally located near the museum entrance, are instead positioned at the entrance to the exhibition spaces on the basement level, alongside a secondary reception

desk. Up to this point, the space retains the qualities of an entrance area while maintaining its urban permeability at the city-level floor. Visitors who are not attending any exhibition can continue to explore other areas of the museum as though they have not entered a distinct boundary, creating the impression of casually passing through rather than consciously entering a defined interior. This spatial configuration demonstrates how traditional spatial organisation can adapt to various uses based on movement. Additionally, the building's structural design fosters a sense of horizontal connectivity between spaces, even across floors. Vertical circulation elements, such as staircases leading to the lower levels, are intentionally unobtrusive, subtly blending into the background. This design enhances the experience of descending toward the collections, creating a deliberate, contemplative, and almost ceremonial journey through the building. During this descent, the visitor's connection to the city remains intact. The linear flow of the space continues to provide views of the city and park, ensuring that the urban context is never lost. Moreover, the visitor does not need to actively decipher the relationship between spaces, as the seamless flow naturally guides movement. This sense of spontaneity within the interior space mirrors the uninterrupted organisation of the city, park, museum building and rooftop, forming a cohesive spatial narrative.

Towards a New Perspective

Globally, museums are increasingly seen as urban projects that transcend the local level, enhance a city's recognition in tourism, support local creative industries, and foster international collaborations. Within the framework of national development goals, urban renewal projects have frequently adopted the approach of commissioning starchitects to design superstar museum buildings, following the so-called Bilbao Effect—a trend that gained momentum in the 2000s. However, the influence of spatial organisation on social well-being, behavioural patterns, and the improvement of societal welfare has underscored the necessity for these buildings—originally planned as part of structural and economic revitalisation strategies—to adhere to effective public strategies focused on local residents. Koolhaas's critique of architecture as a brand in jeopardy, despite its apparent success, highlights the pressing need to redefine the role of architecture. By establishing a reasonable balance between the formal and the social, architecture can be reoriented towards addressing the collective needs of society (as cited in Foster, 2002/2017: 84). This perspective encapsulates the evolving approach to museum design, where social content and public integration are no longer ancillary but central to architectural and urban discourse.

The conclusions drawn in this article cannot be generalised to other museums included in urban development and transformation projects. Undoubtedly, designers, researchers from various disciplines, individuals who experience the space differently, decision-makers, and

implementers will offer diverse evaluations. Nevertheless, the example of the Budapest: Museum of Ethnography stands out as a case that effectively illustrates how a museum can integrate with the city, reflect its continuity with the surrounding environment in its interior spaces, and play a role in fostering urban socialisation. In this respect, the museum aligns with Tzortzi's concept of the "urbanised museum"—a new type of museum that aims to be an integral, dynamic, inclusive, and open part of the city.

This project demonstrates that the museum building is not solely designed as an internally organised structure but is envisioned as part of a larger urban system. It is evident that the morphological structure of the city has been analysed, with connections established from the urban scale to the interior scale, and the building designed to integrate seamlessly with its immediate surroundings. By forming an inseparable relationship with the park and refraining from imposing a towering or obstructive presence relative to the surrounding residential areas, the building creates a sense of ensemble and community. Furthermore, the building supports societal interaction with the city, independent of the museum's opening hours, events, or programmes. This approach shows that even when the museum's spatial functions are limited, its social functions can persist, enabling the creation of a new urban public meaning aligned with everyday social realities and communal existence. In other words, the Budapest: Museum of Ethnography has been constructed as a museum building that fosters the coexistence of various urban elements, embodying a holistic integration with its context.

The only personal conclusion that can be generalised from this case study is as follows: a museum building can connect socially with its urban stakeholders not by being displayed as a consumable icon of popular culture, but through an inclusive design that embraces local and regional values. Museum architecture has the agency to either distance the museum from its urban context or to encompass and integrate all spatial relationships tied to the city. These reflections affirm the necessity of accounting for a range of environmental, contextual, and social attributes in process-oriented urban transformation projects that focus on the social interaction enabled by a building's form.

The study highlights how the Budapest: Museum of Ethnography gains meaning within an urban and social context while underscoring the need to evaluate the project from various perspectives. Assessing the museum building's social and economic impacts—particularly on local creative industries—alongside how the project is perceived by local residents and international visitors, is critical. Additionally, examining how the museum's daily usage dynamics and event-based programmes contribute to the city provides valuable insights. Collecting and interpreting feedback, critiques, and user experiences following the project's completion can contribute to understanding how museums are positioned not merely as architectural objects but as dynamic urban actors. In this regard, conducting an international

comparison, establishing connections with similar projects, and evaluating how this initiative might serve as a model for other cities can offer further contributions to the literature.

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